

HRM in Higher Education Model Competency and Job Matching in Placement

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ABSTRACT: Higher Education Institution (HEIs) in making changes so that their competitive roles and leadership competencies are factors that need to be taken into account. This paper aims to identify the Job Competency Requirement (JCR) of top leader HEI or rector and analyse the matching of person competency with the JCR in order to placement the appropriate leader in order to achieve effective performance. Methodology using competency with called the Behavior Event Interview (BEI), is a semi-structured interview in which the respondent is asked to recall recent, specific events in which he or she felt effective and quantitative methods with surveys using questionnaires. The sample uses HEIs which has excellent institutional accreditation, namely leaders, deans and Heads of Departments (HoD's). The research finding is that the competency requirements for leaders at HEI's are 15 competencies. Practical implications that competency can be used for selection, placement, succession plan, leadership development of HEIs and policy makers concern with leadership development.

KEYWORDS: Competency Dictionary, Job Competency Requirement, Leadership, Job matching, Higher Education.

INTRODUCTION

The transformation of higher education (HEI) in facing RI 4.0 needs to be carried out plus that since 2019 there has been a global health problem, namely the Covid 19 outbreak, HEIs in Indonesia, which is approximately 4000 in number, has transformed learning using E-learning very quickly." For the sake of quality, the Ministry of Research, Technology and Higher Education (MoRTHE) is seriously trying to improve the quality of HEI by making a policy to classify through 4 quality aspects, namely quality management, research, institutional & student affairs. With this classification, HEIs are competing to compete towards improving quality (Kusumastuti & Idrus, 2017). Higher education top leaders play an important role, to be able to realize the performance demands of HEI institutions that continue to reap quality changes that are globally acceptable and able to inspire a strong strategic vision, have a philosophy of excellence in success, a culture of constant reflection, create an organization that learns and changes and develops strategic plan by translating the vision into a real program to innovate higher education.

That the academic leadership of HEI includes rector, vice rector (top leader), Dean for the head of the faculty, the head of study program (HoD) is the head of the department (Eddy, 2010). The effectiveness of HEI's top leaders is reflected in the constant changes that occur in the institution and HEI leaders have the task of being the captain in the flow of change and the leadership of play an important role, in an effort to create the right learning environment, mobility and social access to higher education (Babu, 2016). HEI's Top Leadership is an important issue in this era, a crisis phenomenon leadership at HEI will cause the entire potential of the system to be exhausted.

HE leaders who come from academic often work part time because they too concentrate on keeping up with academic activities where at the end of their term they will return become academics/lecturers again (Spendlove, 2007). Competency is an ability based on intention (*intent*) embodied by behavior that is found to be real or observable in order to predict performance or ability to solve problems in a particular situation. (Boyatzis, 2009; McClelland, 1973; Spencer, 1993; Kusumastuti, 2018; Kusumastuti, 2020).

The relationship between competency and performance is very close because work effectiveness is built on competencies, such as: Figure 1 shows that a person's maximum performance can occur when a person's abilities or talents match needs of work demands or positions and organizational environment. A person's talent is described by: personal values, vision and philosophy, knowledge, competence, life and career, interests and style. Work demands described with responsibilities, roles and tasks that need to be done. Organizational environment depicted through competence, culture and climate, structures and systems as well

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as the strategic position of the industry (Boyatzis, 1982; 2008).

Figure 1. Theory of action and job performance (Boyatzis 1982, 2008)

There are 6 groups of competency that make the difference between a person performing superior and average which can be seen in table 2. namely the competency groups: 1) Cognitive intelligence 2) Emotional intelligence, 3) Self-management, 4) Intelligence social awareness, (5) social awareness and (6) relationship management competency. (Boyatzis, Goleman, & McKee, 2002); (Babu, 2016), Boyatzis et al, (2013) that Social, Emotional and Intellectual/Cognitive Competencies can be used to predict the effectiveness of professional leaders and managers. Based on Dyah Kusumastuti's 2018 research, 15 HEI Leadership competencies were produced, namely: Self Awareness (SA) Self Management (SM), Personal Mastery (PM), Adaptability (AD) Creative Thinking (CT), Teamwork (TW), Communication (CO), Conflict Management (CM), Managing People & Coaching (MP), Self Confidence (SC), Planning (PL), Execution (EX), Improving Organization (IO), Managing System (MT), Entrepreneurship (ET), (Kusumastuti, 2018).

METHODOLOGY

This research is a continuation of previous research that has been published through the Journal (Kusumastuti, D 2018) as described above. Follow-up research was carried out in 2 stages, namely qualitative with structured interviews called Behavior Event Interview (BEI) or CBI Competency Based Interview (CBI) and quantitative with survey methods using ordinal questionnaires. BEI interview technique using questions Situation -Action-Result (SAR): 1) What led up to the situation? (2) Who said or did what to whom? (3) What did you say or do next? What were you thinking and feeling? (4) What was the outcome or result of the event? This is followed by Questionnaire by Top leaders, Dean, HoDs. From the results of BEI developed Model of Competency Dictionary. BEI is based on the premise that Competency is not just a motive for thinking but needs to be followed by evidence of certain behaviors that reflect a motive. The more important a particular competency is to produce effective performance, the more important it is to be evaluated in the selection process. (Kusumastuti, 2012; 2017; Kandula, 2015). As interviewee are 32 HoD and 7 top leaders of HEIs, in this case the top leader from HEIs accredited universities and departments excellent. In a curve, a population with a normal distribution is located on the right hand side of the graph and the number of this is usually between 1-10% of the population or superior is at +1SD, the number in the HEI classification by MoRTHE in 2015 clusters 1 and 2 amounted to 66 HEIs out of 3000 HEIs. The number of samples from 7 HEIs is 10% of the total HEI on clusters 1&2. 2016. The sample used can be explained through Figure 2 below. Superior performance, one standard deviation above the mean, top 15% or roughly top one of 10 employees in a job. These are the Keepers and those falling in the top 2% are the Super keepers (Berger, 2004)

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Source: n Kusumastuti , D 2020

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the ordinal questionnaire for the top competencies of HEI leaders, HoD, were performed with cluster analysis using a multivariate technique, namely the hierarchical method to classify groups of cognate competencies from HoD and HEI. From the results of the competency cluster test for HEI and HoD leaders, a non-parametric statistical test was carried out, namely the difference test with Mann Whitney U which was intended to determine the difference in competency levels between HoDs and HEI Top leaders from ordinal data that were not normally distributed.

Decision making in the Mann Whitney U test is based on the test results if the Asym.Sign value is < 0.05 , then there is a difference between the competency level requirements of the HEI and HoD Top Leader levels. If Asym.Sign. > 0.05 , there is no difference between the two samples.

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The results of the BEI structured interviews are Competency Dictionary which includes 15 competencies which can be seen in table 1, which in the dictionary explains the definition of competency and explains the behavioral indicators of each level. The higher the level, the more complex the behavioral indicators or the more strategic.

Table 1. Model Competency Dictionary of 15 Competencies & behavioral description for each level.

1. Self-Awareness: The ability to pay attention to oneself through understanding moods, emotions and impulses, taking into account the effects of oneself on others, understanding one's limitations.	
Behavioral description for level :	
1/2/3	Takes into account the effect of self on others. Pay attention to the intentions, thoughts, feelings of others. Adopt a positive outlook, increase self-energy
2. Self-Management: The ability to manage oneself as a leader of higher education institutions such as self-control and keep showing academic behavior in the campus world	
Behavior Indicators for level:	
1/2/3	Manage self-emotions to stay positive , remain calm under pressure, maintain one's beliefs, use the abilities & interests of others, express concern for managing time efficiently
3. Personal-Mastery: The ability to continuously improve and self-awareness to remain professional, continuously update knowledge and seek learning opportunities and looking for feedback.	
Behavioral Indicators for level :	
1/2/3	Continually reflect and increase self-awareness with personal beliefs actively seek learning opportunities to develop; committed to continuous personal growth and constantly seek and value the value of personal feedback.
4. Adaptability : The ability to adapt to changes in the environment and take the initiative to manage change effectively, respect differences of opinion, work effectively with various colleagues or different groups. Flexibility in handling Change.	

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Behavioral description for level :	
1	Positive thinking in change. Adapt to defined changes. Keeping work effective & efficient in the face of changing jobs.
2	Evaluate long-term change programs. Developing values, dynamics of change. Change behavior according to the situation.
3.	Creating a forum for exchanging information, knowledge, skills, expertise, learning, experience with stakeholders involved in the organization. Communicating to all levels of the organization. Adjusting the organization's strategy due to major changes.
5. Creative Thinking : Solving problems by thinking analytically and logically, drawing on all sources of data, knowledge and past experiences; linking actions to causes or goals	
Behavioral description for level :	
1	Open mind to new ideas. Make so that there is no status quo. Looking for innovative solutions to problems.
2	Encourage thinking with different perspectives. Creating creative programs for organizational performance. Understand the desired future state and devise creative actions to achieve it Propose new procedures or methods to overcome deficiencies.
3	Making breakthroughs at the organizational level. Creating a vision for the future and developing a frame of reference for achieving it. Provide inspiration for the practice of creative thinking culture. Creating new breakthroughs for effective institutional performance. Make a breakthrough by taking into account the national interest. Creating a creative yet ethical culture.
6. Building Partnership : Establishing, developing cooperation for organizational goals to create a spirit of friendship and trust	
Behavioral description for level:	
1	Increase group productivity, build partnerships. Building cohesion and trust in the team by involving the team in decision making
2	Building cooperative relationships with other organizations, making local or global collaborations according to the needs of the work unit.
3	Making cooperation policies for the purpose of national achievement. Become a role model for staff on global initiatives.
7. Communication: The ability to communicate convincingly through effective techniques such as active listening and interpretation of non-verbal cues. Take the views of colleagues and subordinates.	

Behavioral description for level :	
1	Practice active listening and perceptive interpretation of non-verbal cues to gain a better understanding of other points of view. Convince others. Adopt the right communication style.
2	Seek feedback proactively on issues; Convince others in an open discussion.
3	Build a culture of open communication – dialogue. Communicating a shared vision. Utilize various media to deliver impactful communication to all levels inside & outside the organization
8. Conflict-Management: Manage and resolve conflicts, differences of opinion and resolve disagreement effectively.	
Behavioral description for level :	
1	Identify sources of conflict, Make various parties to be open.
2	Finish by listening, dialogue, discussion. Provide a viable alternative solution.
3	Cultivating conducive conditions. Leads to better resolution of disagreements
9. Managing People & Coaching: Ensuring the development of individuals to reach their potential; provide feedback, coaching & counseling; recognize and reward achievements; motivate and improve their ability helping them grow. Improving their ability concern for organization & work goal.	
Behavioral description for level :	
1	Sharing experiences with colleagues, Recognizing achievements, Realizing the potential of others.
2	Planning the development of individual progress. Identify talents and candidates to become future leaders. Encourage others to make career development plans, Create programs <i>knowledge sharing</i> .
3	Creating a culture of continuous learning / knowledge, Developing leadership in each organizational unit. Establish a system of recognition and rewards.

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10. Self Confidence : A person's belief in his own ability to carry out/complete his job mission	
Behavioral description for level:	
1	Express confidence in his abilities based on consideration of his own abilities.
2	Feel good about challenges. Act to prove his point, be ready for sudden presentations, Express honesty without being pushy.
3	Accept challenges willingly. Enjoys challenges, seeks greater responsibility without being asked.
11. Planning and Organizing : Planning & organizing work according to the needs of the university by responding to the dynamics and changes that will occur, identifying needs and choosing priorities for the benefit of the university.	
Behavioral description for level :	
1	Manage time and resources as well as assets in higher education in order to achieve the set targets. Design and manage a project or task simultaneously efficiently. Identify appropriate and correct methods and processes for managing tasks or jobs.
2	Make an alternative plan (<i>contingency</i>) in anticipation of the task capacity in the unit he leads. Setting targets, designing plans with time allocation for completion. Establishing a monitoring system or monitoring the progress of long-term, medium-term tasks
3	Establishing the Vision of PT. Setting organizational targets realistically, such as setting <i>key performance indicators</i> (KPI) for universities. Perform <i>cascading KPIs</i> , determine how to measure them. Develop alternative plans in anticipation. Analyzing risks in planning.
12. Execution: Utilizing technology, human resources and processes to improve implementation and control, respond to new developments, monitor, evaluate and assess progress, adjust and implement plans, determine, ensure mission fulfillment.	
Behavioral description for level:	
1	Manage resources to maximize effectiveness. Setting standards, monitoring and supervising tasks to achieve goals. Leveraging technology for results orientation.
2	Utilize available technology to ensure mission success. Synergy of resources from various sub-units to improve overall capabilities. Control sub-units to focus on missions. Utilize knowledge management. Manage uncertainty.
3	Utilize new technology to enhance capabilities. Develop accountability at all levels of the organization. Mobilize college assets. Improve organizational performance standards by developing a climate of accountability at all levels.
13. Developing Organization: Initiative in recognizing the need for change; create interest for organizational change, manage and see through change efforts, and continually seek ways to improve the organization.	
Behavioral description for level:	
1	Displays openness-adaptability, operationalizes new ideas. Helping others to adapt to change
2	Identify ways of effective organizational improvement change. Identify change agents. Handle changes in the work unit.
3	Foster an adaptive climate to ensure organizational renewal. Encourage organizational improvement practices and paradigms. Act as an agent of organizational change.
14. Higher Education Management: The ability to use knowledge and skills in managing quality universities is recognized globally.	
Behavioral description for level :	
1	Identifying the study program's business processes. Improve the ability to meet customer needs. Develop a quality management system for work units/study programs. Make efforts to improve service to customers continuously.
2	Identify business processes in the Faculty / School, strive for continuous improvement of service to customers. Build a Quality Management System according to University policies.
3	Establish quality standards and policies, establish a quality management system, establish university management policies and directions. Internalize the value and spirit of service to every individual in the organization, develop best service policy to satisfy customer needs.
15. Entrepreneurship: The ability to create opportunities, new ideas by applying new ways of working, technology, services & products to empower organizations, optimize resources to improve service quality, change the organization's core competencies with services.	
Behavioral description for level :	

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1	Develop resources for optimization. Efforts to manage resources in order to realize the idea. Looks for or finds ways to do things faster or at less cost.
2	Formulate the concept of organizational optimization. Take advantage of opportunities for organizational optimization.
3	Seeks resources from within and outside the organization to carry out the idea. Formulate policies for organizational optimization. Creating a culture of independence by managing financial sources (Financial Acumen). Expresses concern about costs vs benefits of some improvement, change or course action.

Source: Research data & Kusumastuti, D, 2018

The results of the Dendrogram Cluster Test data processing are shown in Figure 3, there are two competencies level clusters, meaning that there is a cluster grouping of the HEI top leadership competency level (7 samples top Leader) and the HoD leadership cluster (32 HoD's). This means that the top leadership group or rectorate has a different level of job competency requirement from the HoD group.

Table 2 shown are different test results with statistical tests with Mann Whitney, between the Top leadership competency group / rectorate and HoDs, shown in table 2 where the significance value for all competencies is < 0.05 ; means that there is a difference in the level or level of competency needs between the rectorate leadership and HoD leader. Except Sign. SA : 0.07 and sign. SM : 0.06, but because SA and SM for *level* 1.2.3 have the same contents (table 1), means that competency level need for rectorate leadership -top leader and HoD is also the same. Table 3 shown the results of the choice with the ordinal questionnaire that the competency needs (JCR) for the rectorate are required *level* 3, and JCR for HoDs required *level* 1. As for the dean, it is assumed that between the study program and the rectorate there is a competency requirement at *level* 2.

Figure 3. Analysis results from SPSS showing the Dendrogram, the Cluster of rectorate and Cluster of HoD competencies level.

Table 2. The Significance Value of the Mann Whitney Difference test results between rectorate competency level & HoD cluster

Competency	Sign.	Competency	Sign.	Competency	Sign.
Sel-Awareness (SA)	0,07	Building Partnership (BP)	0,00	Planning &Organizing (PL)	0,00
Self Management (SM)	0,06	Communication (CO)	0,00	Execution (EX)	0,00
Personal Mastery (PM)	0,00	Conflict Management (CM)	0,00	Entrepreneurship (ET)	0,00
Adaptability (AD)	0,00	Managing People& Coaching (MP)	0,00	Developing Organization (DO)	0,00
Creative Thinking(CT)	0,00	Self Confidence (SC)	0,00	Higher Education Management (HEM)	0,00

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Table 3. Job Competency Requirement (JCR) of HEI Leaders

Leadership Level		Competency		
		Self Awareness	Building Partnership	Planning & Organizing
Rector	Level 3	Self Management	Communication	Execution
Dean	Level 2	Personal mastery	Conflict Management	Improving Organization
HoD	Level 1	Adaptability	Managing People & Coaching	HE Management

Source: results of research data processing

Competency with indicators behavior level 3, is the JCR rectorate/Top leader which is the competency level for strategic leadership. Level 2 is a level of operational competency such as a dean and 1 is a level of competency for leadership that directly handles members of an organization such as HoD.

DISCUSSION

Individual leaders in higher education can build their leadership or prepare to become HEI leaders at every level by using the 15 competency dictionaries in table 3. Developing leadership competencies is not enough with training. Development is not the same as training, self-development, learning interpersonal skills is important for building leadership. (Kusumastuti, D 2012), HEI leaders in the midst of quality competition and Knowledge Society need effective leadership competencies, namely someone who can manage their own energy and the energy of others around the organizational environment. The energy in question is how much people are involved in the organization physically, emotionally, spiritually and socially (Kusumastuti, 2012). So that HEI as a knowledge enterprise continues to innovate and produce knowledge for welfare and improve the quality of life of the community. .

The results of table 1 competency dictionary 15 can be used as a job competency guideline which is a guideline for describing the behavior attitudes needed in carrying out job duties, this position competency can complete job descriptions in job analysis and can be used as knowledge management. Where the head of the work unit in the HEI environment with the same competence can jointly use the knowledge contained in the competency dictionary, exchange knowledge and practical experience and develop this knowledge to be applied as a standard method in the HEI environmental work unit. Cross-functional and cross-organizational communication can be done more clearly and accurately by using standardized terms of competence, making it more possible to make optimal use of the capabilities of employees in various parts of the work unit.

The positive relationship between emotional, social and work performance, lack of self-awareness, emotional intelligence capital, results in negative performance consequences for leaders, Hopkins 2008. There is evidence to suggest that the greater the overall level of emotional and social intelligence a person exhibits, the more likely it is the leader will be considered an outstanding player. Boyatzis & McKee, (2005), suggested that resonant leaders are defined as individuals who have built resonant relationships around them through emotional and social intelligence. Shared vision becomes important in leadership in creating a positive culture of change and difference that brings growth in the organization.

Use of Competence in placing the top leader in HEI's

Top leader placement in HEI should go through a selection with 15 Competencies research findings can be used as *Job-person matching*, namely the process of matching between JCR & Competencies of the candidate.

Competence which consists of real behavior, knowledge and skills can be observed, so that it is not just knowledge, but knowledge that is used in certain behavioral actions, skills that can be realized to produce effective performance. Competence is not just a thought motive, but has been in the form of certain behavioral actions that describe a motive. Competencies identified as job requirements can produce effective performance, so it is important to evaluate them in the selection process. Past performance or *track record* can be used to predict the competencies a person has needed in a position. If someone has certain competencies, it can be used to predict future performance.

Evidence of past behavioral actions can be used to predict future behavior (Kusumastuti, 2010). To carry out the selection process for HEI leaders, it is necessary to create a practice culture of *Having the Right People in the Right Place*. Simulation *Job-person matching* , shown in table 4 .

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Table 4. Simulasi Kompetensi Job -Person Matching Analysis

No	Competency	JCR- Level for Rector/Top Leader	Person Competency	Competency Difference /Gap
1	Self Awareness (SA)	3	3	0
2	Self Management (SM)	3	3	0
3	Personal Mastery (PM)	3	3	0
4	Adaptability (AD)	3	1	2
5	Creative-Thinking CT)	3	1	2
6	Building Partnership (BP)	3	1	2
7	Communication (CO)	3	1	2
8	Conflict Management (CM)	3	1	2
9	Managing People & Coaching (MP)	3	1	2
10	Self Confidence (SC)	3	1	2
11	Planning & Organizing (PL)	3	2	1
12	Execution (EX)	3	1	2
13	Developing Organization)	3	2	1
14	HEI Management (HEM)	3	3	0
15	Entrepreneurship (ET)	3	2	1
	Total	45	26	19

Compatibility of Person Competency who are as candidates with job competency requirements (Job-person matching) :

% Mismatch = $19/45 * 100\% = 43\%$.

% Fit = $1 - \% \text{ Mismatch} = 57\%$

The suitability of the candidate's competence with the HEI Top leader position is 57%. Furthermore, this data is calculated for table 4, namely the results of the assessment in the form of a match (% Fit). Or it can also be calculated from the Competency. The top leader selection model for HEIs above, requirements, credibility, integrity and achievement trends as well as track record taken can complete the assessment of leader candidates, it is hoped that there will be no conflict of interest. The selected candidates are expected to be able to realize the quality of HEI so that they are highly competitive. The selection model in this placement needs to be a core element of the organizational culture at HEI and in the behavioral norms practiced by every academic community (Bossidy, 2005). So that the top leaders of HEI are academics, administration & leaders of HEI as Knowledge Enterprise who produce knowledge together with the academic community with various strengths possessed by organizational members, especially lecturers so as to produce knowledge that is used for the welfare of society.

CONCLUSION

The top leader of HEI as the leader of the flow of change requires a series of competencies. The issue of determining the leadership of PT from the election to selection method is important for government policies, especially the Ministry of Education and Culture and needs to become HEI's own awareness to prepare its prospective leaders through a succession plan to prevent the phenomenon of leadership crisis in Higher Education.

To be a highly effective leader; not enough training, need development of interpersonal skills; development does not mean training; and activities outside of work are important in developing leadership competencies.

Successful clear how important the role and quality of leadership (CEO or Chancellor or President of University, Dean, HoD and other leadership positions) and high-quality management systems are following the times, "*The New Indonesian University*" immediately materialized.

At the end, the top leader of a university is a person who has a great desire to make the nation's competitiveness & loves the journey of life as a high-quality HEI leader, working for the beneficial endeavor.

In the end, my motivation for this research personally is that because I am a higher education administrator, the competency findings in this research can be used to build and become a template for becoming a successful administrative leader. And my firm belief that this research will complete the circle of life.

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